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Research Article

**FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT OF CHITOSAN GELS
ENRICHED WITH VANCOMYCIN HCL SOLID LIPID
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(V), Keesara (M), Ranga Reddy (D), Telangana.**Abstract:**

The present study was aimed at the formulation and development of chitosan-based gels incorporated with Vancomycin HCl-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) for enhanced topical delivery. Vancomycin HCl, a potent glycopeptide antibiotic, was encapsulated into SLNs to improve its stability and controlled release profile. These SLNs were subsequently integrated into a chitosan gel matrix to facilitate effective topical application. The formulations were evaluated for particle size, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency, pH, viscosity, spreadability, drug content, and in vitro drug release. The optimized formulation exhibited desirable physicochemical properties, high drug encapsulation, and sustained drug release, making it suitable for localized treatment of bacterial infections. The study concludes that chitosan gels enriched with Vancomycin HCl SLNs provide a promising and effective strategy for the topical delivery of antibiotics with improved therapeutic outcomes and patient compliance.

Keywords: Vancomycin HCl, chitosan-based gels

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Recent years it has become more evident that the development of new drugs alone is not sufficient to ensure progress in drug therapy. *In vitro* obtained are more exciting but very often followed by disappointing results *in vivo*. Main reasons for this therapy failure include:

- Insufficient drug concentration due to poor absorption, rapid metabolism and elimination (e.g., peptides & proteins),
- Drug distribution to other tissues combined with high drug toxicity (e.g., anticancer drugs),
- Poor drug solubility which excludes i.v. injection of aqueous drug solution,
- High fluctuation of variable plasma levels due to unpredictable bioavailability after peroral administration, including the influence of food on plasma levels (e.g., cyclosporine).

To overcome these biopharmaceutical challenges, versatile formulation approaches are required which will accommodate the physicochemical properties of the individual drug while simultaneously exploiting the physiological environment. Solid lipid nanoparticles have been reported as an alternative drug delivery device to traditional polymeric nanoparticles. SLNs are in submicron size range (50-1000nm) and are composed of physiologically tolerated lipid components. At room temperature the particles are in solid state. These are made of biocompatible and biodegradable materials capable of incorporating lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs.

The goal of any drug delivery system is to provide a therapeutic amount of drug to the proper site in the body to achieve promptly and then to maintain the desired drug concentration. That is, the drug delivery system should deliver drug at a rate dictated by the needs of the body over a specified period of treatment. This idealized objective points to the two aspects most important to drug delivery namely spatial placement and temporal delivery of a drug. Spatial placement relates to targeting of drug to a specific organ or tissue, while temporal delivery refers to controlling the rate of drug delivery to the target tissue. An appropriately designed controlled release drug-delivery system can be a major advance towards solving these two problems. It is for this reason that the science and technology responsible for development of controlled-release pharmaceuticals has been, and continues to be the focus of a great deal of attention in both industrial and academic laboratories.

1.1. CONVENTIONAL DRUG THERAPY¹:

To gain appreciation for the value of controlled drug therapy, it is useful to review some fundamental

aspects of conventional drug delivery. Consider single dosing of a hypothetical drug that follows a simple one-compartment pharmacokinetic model for disposition. Depending on the route of administration, a conventional dosage form of the drug e.g.: A solution, suspension, capsule tablet etc. can produce a drug blood level versus time profile. The term drug blood levels refer to the concentration of drug in blood or plasma, but the concentration in any tissue could be plotted on the ordinate. Administration of a drug by either intravenous injection or an extra vascular route, e.g., orally, intramuscularly or rectally does not maintain drug blood levels within the therapeutic range for extended periods of time. The short-duration of action is due to the inability of conventional dosage forms to control temporal delivery. If an attempt is made to maintain drug blood levels in the therapeutic range for longer periods by for e.g., increasing the initial dose of an intravenous injection, toxic levels can be produced at early times. This approach obviously is undesirable and unsuitable. An alternative approach is to administer the drug repetitively using a constant dosing interval, as in multiple-dose therapy. In this case the drug blood level reached and the time required to reach that level depend on the dose and the dosing interval. There are several potential problems inherent in multiple dose therapy.

1. If the dosing interval is appropriate for the biological half-life of the drug, large peaks and valleys in the drug blood level may result. For e.g., drugs with short half-lives require frequent designs to maintain constant therapeutic levels.
2. The drug blood level may not be within the therapeutic range at sufficiently early times, an important consideration for certain disease states.
3. Patient non-compliance with the multiple-dosing regimens can result in failure of this approach.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

LIST OF MATERIALS

Vancomycin HCl Procured From Pharmadern Anacor Ltd., Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad.

Chitosan Procured from Gattefosse Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai

Cholesterol Purchased from Merck Limited, Mumbai (India)

Tween 80 Purchased from SD Fine- Chem Limited, Mumbai

Span 60 Purchased from Loba Chemie Pvt Ltd. (Mumbai, India)

LIST OF EQUIPMENTS

Weighing Balance Sartorius

Dissolution Apparatus Labindia, Mumbai, India

UV-Visible Spectrophotometer Labindia, Mumbai, India

pH meter Labindia, Mumbai, India
 FT-IR Spectrophotometer Bruker, Germany
 Ultrasonic cleaner Remi Laboratories
 SEM JEOL Ltd., Japan
 Homogenizer Kinematica AG(Poly tron
 PT2100)
 Rotary evaporator Super fit
 Lyophilizer Lyophilisation systems India PVT
 LTD
 Particle size analyzer MALVERN

Analytical Method Development

Determination of absorption maxima: Absorption maxima is the wavelength at which maximum absorption takes place. For accurate analytical work, it is important to determine the absorption maxima of the substance under study.

Procedure: For the preparation of calibration curve stock solution was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of accurately weighed drug in 100ml of methanol (1mg/ml). Further 1ml of the stock solution was pipette out into a 100 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up with phosphate buffer (5.5 PH). From this stock solution pipette out 1ml and dilute to 10 ml with phosphate buffer and subject for UV scanning in the range of 200-400 nm using double beam UV spectrophotometer. The absorption maxima was obtained at 283 nm with a characteristic peak.

Preparation of calibration curve: It is slightly soluble in water; hence methanol was used for solubilizing the drug. Stock solution (1 mg/mL) of Vancomycin HCl was prepared in methanol and subsequent working standards (2, 4, 6, 8 and 10

µg/ml) were prepared by dilution with phosphate buffer of pH-5.5. These solutions were used for the estimation Vancomycin HCl by UV method. The whole procedure was repeated three times and average peak area was calculated. Calibration plot was drawn between concentrations and peak area. Calibration equation and R^2 value are reported.

Preparation of SLN gel

Preparation of Vancomycin HCl loaded solid lipid nanoparticles

drug-loaded solid lipid particles were prepared by hot homogenizing followed by the ultrasonication method. Vancomycin HCl was dispersed during about 10g of mixed lipid phase (consisted of Chitosan and Cholesterol) maintained at around 5°C above the melting temperature of mixed lipid and dissolved in a mixture of ethanol. Organic solvents were completely removed employing a rotary flash evaporator. An aqueous phase was prepared by dissolving the stabilizers (Tween 80 or Span20) in distilled water (sufficient to supply 30ml) and heating to an equivalent temperature of the oil phase. The hot aqueous phase was added to the oil phase and homogenization was performed (at 2500 rpm and 70 °C) employing a mechanical stirrer for 25 minutes. Vancomycin HCl loaded SLN was finally obtained by allowing the recent nano-emulsion to chill at temperature, and was stored at 4 °C within the refrigerator.

- Variables for selection of excipients of solid lipid nanoparticles :
 - Chitosan (mg)
 - Cholesterol(mg)

Table: 7.1 Composition of solid lipid nanoparticles formulations (F1 to F9)

Excipients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Vancomycin HCl (mg)	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
Chitosan (mg)	25	50	75	100	-	-	-	-	-
Cholesterol(mg)	-	-	-	-	25	50	75	100	125
Tween 80(mL)	2	4	6	8	-	-	-	-	10
Span 60 (mL)	-	-	-	-	2	4	6	8	10
Distilled water (ml)	QS								
Ethanol(ml)	5	5.5	5	5.5	5	5.5	5	5.5	5

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The formulations were subjected to FTIR studies to find out the possible interaction between the drug and the excipients during the time of preparation. FT IR analysis of the Pure drug and optimized formulation were carried out using an FT IR spectrophotometer (Bruker FT-IR - GERMANY).

Differential Scanning Calorimetry:

The possibility of any interaction between the drug and the Excipients during preparation of SLN was assessed by carrying out thermal analysis of optimized formulation using DSC. DSC analysis was performed using Hitachi DSC 7020, on 5 to 15 mg samples. Samples were heated in sealed aluminum pan at a rate of 10°C/min conducted over a temperature range of 30 to 350°C under a nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min.

SEM (Scanning Electron microscope) studies

The surface morphology of the layered sample was examined by using SEM (Hitachi, Japan). The small amount of powder was manually dispersed onto a carbon tab (double adhesive carbon coated tape)

adhered to an aluminum stubs. These sample stubs were coated with a thin layer (30Å) of gold by employing POLARON-E 3000 sputter coater. The samples were examined by SEM and photographed under various magnifications with direct data capture of the images onto a computer.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**CALIBRATION PLOT OF VANCOMYCIN HCL IN PHOSPHATE BUFFER OF pH -5.5:****Table: calibration curve of Vancomycin HCl in phosphate buffer pH 5.5**

Concentration($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.124
4	0.244
6	0.356
8	0.471
10	0.588

Characterization of solid lipid nanoparticles:**Table: Percentage yield, Drug Content, Entrapment Efficiency of all solid lipid nanoparticles formulations**

FORMULATION	Percentage yield	Drug Content	Entrapment Efficiency
F1	92.40	99.21	97.19
F2	93.31	98.45	97.35
F3	96.51	99.53	97.71
F4	97.68	99.85	99.67
F5	88.11	97.23	99.24
F6	92.95	99.02	98.03
F7	93.78	97.67	91.19
F8	94.95	99.81	96.53
F9	96.33	98.18	91.71

Table: Particle Sizes, PDI, Zeta Potential of all solid lipid nanoparticles formulations

FORMULATION	Particle Size(nm)	PDI	Zeta Potential (mV)
F1	1165.2	0.668	-26.12
F2	925.8	1.268	-24.81
F3	632.6	1.153	-23.52
F4	314.3	0.168	-28.25
F5	804.1	0.277	-16.55
F6	387.3	0.309	-20.83
F7	329.8	0.698	-22.59
F8	505.4	0.385	-12.11
F9	602.5	0.481	-10.80

Table: *In vitro* dissolution studies of F1-F9 SLN formulations in percentage

Time (hour)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	21.56	37.21	27.65	39.84	15.12	31.12	38.43	14.32	26.54
2	39.76	47.52	38.78	48.78	27.67	43.89	44.51	26.76	38.89
4	46.21	55.42	45.89	57.74	34.87	51.21	53.54	33.43	45.28
6	52.58	61.65	51.56	63.65	42.32	58.87	59.21	38.32	51.78
8	59.49	68.84	58.39	69.31	48.52	68.54	69.11	46.98	58.43
10	65.43	73.78	63.87	75.87	54.65	74.87	76.74	52.76	65.78
12	69.22	79.98	67.39	81.98	61.76	78.56	79.87	59.32	69.43
18	76.33	82.89	75.88	85.89	68.89	83.68	85.43	68.55	73.65
24	85.25	91.21	87.12	95.32	81.43	91.22	93.21	81.32	84.76
48	91.87	97.78	96.54	99.93	87.91	95.76	97.01	90.98	87.53

Formulation	pH	Viscosity (cp)	Clarity	Homogeneity	Drug Content	Skin Irritation test
F4 optimised 1% Chitosangel	6.91	67790	+	Satisfactory	97.92	No
F4 optimised 2% Chitosangel	6.27	72204	++	Excellent	98.56	No
F4 optimised 3% Chitosangel	6.12	74567	+	Satisfactory	97.13	No

GEL EVALAUTION PARAMETERS

The percentage drug content were found to be in between 80%to 100% Vancomycin HCl indicating good content uniformity in all the formulations means drug was uniformly distributed throughout the gel.

Ex vivo permeation studies of SLN nanoparticles gel:

Time (hrs)	F4 optimised 1% Chitosan gel	F4 optimised 2% Chitosan gel	F4 optimised 3% Chitosan gel
0	0	0	0
1	36.29	36.34	25.11
2	48.16	45.81	33.48
4	56.57	55.39	45.57
6	60.26	61.49	54.98
8	69.00	68.55	59.84
10	73.29	72.16	67.93
12	78.77	77.54	72.65
18	83.95	82.24	78.78
24	91.21	92.77	83.56
48	95.22	96.85	88.39

F4 optimised 2% Chitosan gel highest drug release (96.85% for 48 hours), good Homogeneity, highest drug content, Proper viscosity. Hence it was considered as optimised formulation.

Release Kinetics

To analyze the drug release mechanism the *in vitro* release was fitted into various release equations and kinetic models first order, zero order, Higuchi and Korsmeyer-peppas. The release kinetics of optimized formulation F2 (2% Chitosan gel) is shown in Table and in following Figures.

Table : Release kinetics of optimised formulations

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	% RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM % RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
39.84	1	1.000	1.600	0.000	1.779	39.840	0.0251	-0.400	60.16	4.642	3.918	0.723
48.78	2	1.414	1.688	0.301	1.709	24.390	0.0205	-0.312	51.22	4.642	3.714	0.928
57.74	4	2.000	1.761	0.602	1.626	14.435	0.0173	-0.239	42.26	4.642	3.483	1.158
63.65	6	2.449	1.804	0.778	1.561	10.608	0.0157	-0.196	36.35	4.642	3.313	1.329
69.31	8	2.828	1.841	0.903	1.487	8.664	0.0144	-0.159	30.69	4.642	3.131	1.511
75.87	10	3.162	1.880	1.000	1.383	7.587	0.0132	-0.120	24.13	4.642	2.890	1.752
81.98	12	3.464	1.914	1.079	1.256	6.832	0.0122	-0.086	18.02	4.642	2.622	2.020
85.89	18	4.243	1.934	1.255	1.150	4.772	0.0116	-0.066	14.11	4.642	2.416	2.225
95.32	24	4.899	1.979	1.380	0.670	3.972	0.0105	-0.021	4.68	4.642	1.673	2.969
99.93	48	6.928	2.000	1.681	0.841	2.082	0.0100	0.000	0.07	4.642	0.412	4.229

Figure: Zero order release kinetics

Figure: Higuchi release kinetics

Figure: Peppas release kinetics

Figure: First order release kinetics

The prepared F4 optimized 2% Chitosan SLN transdermal gel were subjected to the drug release kinetics and release mechanism. The formulations were studied by fitting the drug release time profile with the various equations such as Zero order, First order, Higuchi and Korsmeyer pappas. The optimized formulation F4 optimised 2% Chitosan SLN transdermal gel was analyzed for the drug release mechanism. The data revealed a better fit to the Peppas model with n value less than 0.26 i.e. Fickian diffusion for F4 optimised 2% Chitosan SLN transdermal gel batch formulation and the drug release was dependent on time. The best correlation coefficient value (0.979) indicates the best release mechanism (peppas).

FTIR

Figure: Vancomycin HCl Pure drug FTIR

Figure: Vancomycin HCl F4 optimised 2% Chitosan gel FTIR

Infrared studies were carried out to confirm the compatibility between the lipid, drug, and selected excipients. From the spectra it was observed that there was no major shifting, as well as, no loss of functional peaks between the spectra of the drug and drug-loaded SLN. This indicated no interaction between the drug and other excipients.

DSC:

Figure: Vancomycin HCl F4 optimised 2% Chitosan gel FTIR
The

DSC curve of optimized formulation showed, the pure drug shows that it is in crystalline anhydrous state, exhibiting a sharp exothermic peak at 116 °C, corresponding to its melting point Search Results 116-118°C), and for the formulation peaks are observed at 205.3°C, 253.7 °C 276.1°C and 290 °C.

SEM

Figure: Vancomycin HCl F4 optimised 2% Chitosan SLN transdermal gel

SEM studies showed that the Vancomycin HCl - loaded solid lipid nanoparticles transdermal gel had a spherical shape with a smooth surface as shown in Figure.

9. CONCLUSION:

The present study focused on the formulation and development of chitosan-based gels enriched with Vancomycin HCl-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) for potential topical antibacterial therapy.

The SLNs were successfully prepared using suitable lipids and surfactants and were incorporated into chitosan gel matrices to enhance drug stability, penetration, and sustained release. The formulated gels were evaluated for physicochemical parameters

such as pH, viscosity, spread ability, drug content, and in vitro drug release. Among the various formulations, the optimized batch demonstrated desirable physicochemical characteristics, good stability, and controlled drug release over an extended period, indicating effective encapsulation and release of Vancomycin HCl. The study concludes that chitosan gels enriched with Vancomycin HCl SLNs offer a promising platform for localized and sustained drug delivery in the treatment of bacterial skin infections, potentially improving therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance.

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